

Centre for
Data Analytics

Insight

Oireachtas Metadata Project

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Data Summary

- Cleaned dataset contains 86,449 records, described by 27 fields. Stored in CSV and JSON formats.

```
{
  "0": {
    "Approx Place": false,
    "Approx Publication Date": false,
    "Authors": null,
    "Control Number": null,
    "Corporate Author": null,
    "Date Laid": 1529971200000,
    "Description": null,
    "D\u00e9l\u00e9gated Order Paper": null,
    "D\u00e9l\u00e9gated Order Paper Date": null,
    "Laid Before": "D\u00e9l\u00e9gated and Seanad",
    "Language": null,
    "Legislation": "European Union (scrutiny) act 2002 -- Section 2(1)",
    "Motion of Approval": "No",
    "Notes": "application/pdf",
    "Originating Authority": "[\"Department of Communications, Climate Action and Environment\"]",
    "Other Title": null,
    "Place": null,
    "Publication Date": 2018,
    "Publisher": null,
    "Seanad Order Paper": null,
    "Seanad Order Paper Date": null,
    "Statutory Period": null,
    "Subcollection": null,
    "Subjects": "[\"DL\"]",
    "Title": "Council regulation establishing a dedicated financial programme for decommissioning
      of nuclear facilities and management of radioactive waste, and repealing Council
      Regulation (Euratom) No 1368/2013",
    "Year Laid": 2018,
    "index": 0
  }
}
```

JSON Sample

Missing Value Analysis

- In the cleaned dataset, 21 of 27 fields contain missing values.

Analysis of Year Laid

- The *Year Laid* field ranges from 1922 to 2019, with 730 missing values (0.84% of total documents).

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Analysis of Year Laid

- 37,731 documents have been laid since 2000 (44% of all documents). The most active year for publication was 2006.

Analysis of Subjects

- "Subjects should be Library of Congress subject headings or formatted in the same way"
- 39,581 missing values for this field (45.8% of all documents).
- 18,841 documents have two or more subjects.
- 7,107 unique subjects.
- The generic value "DL" dominates this field, appearing in 15.5% documents.

	Count	% Documents
DL	13385	15.483
Finance, Public - Accounting	1927	2.229
War & emergency legislation	1755	2.030
Appropriations & expenditures	1555	1.799
Economic forecasting	1131	1.308
Military policy	577	0.667
Civil service - Examinations	547	0.633
European Union	518	0.599
National monuments - Law & legislation	452	0.523
Finance, Public	434	0.502
Universities & colleges - Employees - Salaries	359	0.415
Imports	357	0.413

Analysis of Subjects

- Excluding the "DL" subject, we can look at the top-20 other most frequently appearing subjects.

Temporal Analysis of Subjects

- By comparing *Subjects* to *Year Laid*, we can look at the frequency of appearance of certain subjects over time.

Analysis of Originating Authority

- "We interpret this [field] as the department laying the document, for example the Dept of Education laying the annual report of the Teaching Council."
- 12,437 missing values (14.4% of all documents).
- 1,347 unique values.
- Some authority names contain abbreviations e.g. "Dept Health" vs "Department of Health".

	Count	% Documents
Department of Finance	8668	10.027
Department of the Taoiseach	4877	5.641
Department of Industry & Commerce	3566	4.125
Department of Foreign Affairs	2002	2.316
Department of Enterprise, Trade & Employment	1926	2.228
Department of Justice, Equality & Law Reform	1781	2.060
Department of Health	1698	1.964
Department of Agriculture, Fisheries & Food	1546	1.788
Department of Health & Children	1363	1.577
Department of Justice & Equality	1296	1.499
Department of Communications, Marine & Natural Resources	1224	1.416
Department of Justice	1147	1.327
Department of Education & Science	1112	1.286
Houses of the Oireachtas	1074	1.242

Analysis of Originating Authority

Temporal Analysis of Originating Authority

- By comparing *Originating Authority* to *Year Laid*, we can look at authority trends over time.

Analysis of Corporate Authors

- *Corporate Author* field "covers the name of the department, agency, state body or committee related to the document".
- 767 missing values (0.9% of total documents)
- 5,746 documents have two or more corporate authors.
- Again from the counts for this field, we see the changing structure of government departments.
- Frequency rankings for *Corporate Author* are similar to the *Originating Authority* field, but not identical.

	Count	% Documents
Dept Agriculture, Fisheries & Food	1378	1.594
Dept Agriculture & Fisheries	375	0.434
Dept Fisheries & Forestry	175	0.202
Dept Fisheries	81	0.094
Dept Tourism, Fisheries & Forestry	44	0.051
Dept Lands & Fisheries	8	0.009

Example: *Corporate Author* values containing both "Fish" and "Dept".

Analysis of Corporate Authors

Temporal Analysis of Corporate Authors

- Temporal trends for *Corporate Author* field are very similar but not identical to those for the *Originating Authority* field.

Analysis of Place

- Look at the place of publication - "usually the head office of the corporate body or agency responsible for the document".
- Some values appear to be approximate, rather than definitive.
- Top list dominated by "Dublin".

Analysis of Document Titles

- We can examine the content of document *titles*, "taken from the cover page or first page. Sometimes titles are improvised if there is no title on a document."
- Titles contained 17,825 unique words, after non-informative "stopwords" were removed.

Analysis of Document Titles

- We can examine the content of document *titles*, "taken from the cover page or first page. Sometimes titles are improvised if there is no title on a document."
- We also look at the most common two-word phrases ("bigrams") which appear in titles.

Temporal Analysis of Document Titles

- We can identify trends for certain sub-strings in document titles over time, relative to the *Year Laid* of the documents.

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Analysis of Sub-collection

- Sub-collection "only used for a small number of documents, particularly Statutory Instruments and Committee Reports."
- Available for 25,905 documents (29.97% of total).

Category	# Documents	% Total Documents
Missing	60544	70.03
Statutory Instrument	22744	26.31
Committee Report	2834	3.28
EU Weekly Report	238	0.28
Post-enactment Report	58	0.07
Committee Debates	15	0.02
Northern Ireland	15	0.02

Analysis of Legislation

- Analyse name of legislation associated with each document.
- 43,967 missing values (50.86% of total documents).
- Count the frequency of each associated piece of legislation, discarding section details.

Analysis of Legislation

- We also extracted the year of the legislation, if provided. Years were extracted for 40,653 documents.

Analysis of Legislation

- Next we analysed words appearing in the legislation names.
- Legislation names contained 1,507 distinct words, after non-informative "stopwords" were removed.

Temporal Analysis of Legislation

- We can look at occurrences of certain sub-strings in legislation names over time. Note that dates correspond to *Year Laid* of the document laid, rather than the year of the legislation.

Analysis of Motions of Approval

- *Motion required* field indicates if a motion of approval was required by the legislation associated with the document.
- 123 missing values (0.15% of total documents)
- Vast majority of values indicate no approval required.

Category	# Documents	% Total Documents
No	85109	98.45
Dáil	547	0.63
Dáil and Seanad	328	0.38
Yes	318	0.37
Missing	125	0.15
Dáil only	17	0.02
Seanad	5	0.01